

ISSUES OF INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE METHODOLOGY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT. *The article discusses the new types of pedagogical methods in teaching English and the methods of its application in the classroom, as well as the practical importance of the effective use of methods. Therefore, it is noted that these methods are useful for students to master another language and speak it fluently.*

Keywords: *method, English, effective, education, student, foreign language ICT.*

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of foreign languages is the key to success in today's world. In the context of globalization, the rapid development of communication and information exchange has increased the need to learn foreign languages. This creates the need to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in the educational system, to use modern and effective methods, in particular, new technologies. New technologies will fundamentally change the educational process, making it more interactive, interesting and, most importantly, effective. They serve to increase student motivation, provide a personalized approach, increase practice, expand access, and ease the work of teachers. It should be noted that new methods and requirements for foreign language teaching and assessment of foreign language teachers' knowledge and skills have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language has also increased day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television

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programs;

— use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;
- CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

— In the course of foreign language lessons, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical educational technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Advanced methods serve as a compos in mastering a foreign language. One such method is the use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson.

Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment during the lesson.

For example: in case 1, old friends meet by chance. Case 2: A child who does not follow the rules of the road while crossing the road, that is, crosses the road where there is no crossing. Case 3. A customer enters the store to buy food. 4 Scenes of these situations are performed. Such life-like role-playing games create a language environment in the course of the lesson, and give students the opportunity to freely express their thoughts. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to freely express their emotional states in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. Making a mistake and correcting it also helps to learn the language and teaches students to pronounce correctly. The use of role-playing games during the lesson ensures that all students are actively involved in the lesson at the same time. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, cheerful atmosphere for the lesson. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

The next method is "Case-study" in English, ("case" is a specific situation, event, "study" - to learn, to analyze) is a method aimed at the implementation of teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations.

One of the most interesting methods is to divide into 3 groups in the game "Pantomimo". One person from each group is put on the board. They are given different words based on the list. They have to explain the words to the rest of the group through gestures and actions without saying a word.

To use this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read and the end of the story is referred to the judgment of the students; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle; - "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yazdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use various games

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in the classroom to interest students in the lesson, for example, "Pantomime" (pantomime), this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired; - "A chain story" method helps students to develop oral speech; "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students; - "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people; - The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic; - Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, and the active movement of the student in the educational process are envisaged.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the use of new technologies in foreign language teaching significantly improves the educational process and helps students to learn the language effectively. As a result of the use of innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers can make our contribution by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

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